

PREVALENCE AND ANTIMICROBIAL SUSCEPTIBILITY OF KLEBSIELLA SPECIES IN CLINICAL SPECIMENS OF BOTH INDOOR AND OUTDOOR PATIENTS OF TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, RAWALPINDI

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Abstract

Klebsiella spp. are Gram negative, non-motile, usually capsulated rods. They are frequently found in the large intestine but are also present in soil and water. These organisms are usually opportunistic pathogens that cause nosocomial infections, especially urinary tract and respiratory tract infections. *Klebsiella* species often produces beta-lactamases and are resistant to ampicillin. Cephalosporins and aminoglycosides are used to treat *Klebsiella* infections. Some *Klebsiella* strains show multiple drug resistance and are an important cause of hospital acquired infections. The aim of this study is to determine the prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility patterns of *Klebsiella* species. Purely isolated colonies of *Klebsiella* spp. were obtained, biochemical tests and gram staining were performed for identification. Isolated colonies will be streaked on Mueller Hinton agar plate for antibiotic sensitivity testing. The antibiotic susceptibility test will be determined according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) interpretive criteria. An antibiotic impregnated disk will be placed on MH agar and inoculated with the test bacterium. A clear zone or ring will be formed around an antibiotic disk after incubation if the agent inhibits bacterial growth. According to antibiogram results of 143 isolates of *K. pneumoniae*, the highest antibiotic resistance was related to amoxicillin-clavulanate (98%), cefexime (96.70%) and cefotaxime (97%) and 96.60% isolates were susceptible to colistin. Isolates also show susceptibility to gentamicin (82%), amikacin (78.10%), tigecycline (75.50%), sulzone (69.20%), imipenem (56%). It also shows resistance to cotrimoxazole (89%), ceftriaxone (87.49%), ciprofloxacin (79%), ceftazidime (86.30%).

INTRODUCTION

The tribe *Klebsiella*, which is a part of the Enterobacteriaceae family, includes the genus *Klebsiella*. The organisms are named for German microbiologist Edwin Klebs, who lived in the 19th century. (1) It is an opportunistic pathogen capable of causing a wide range of community-acquired and hospital-acquired infections, such as urinary tract infections (UTIs), respiratory tract infections and infections of wounds and soft tissue. (3) It has in recent years become one of the world's leading causes of nosocomial infections, with an increasing mortality rate, particularly in immunocompromised individuals, neonates and the elderly.

It is also increasingly implicated in severe community-acquired infections such as pneumonia and meningitis. (4) On their cell surfaces, members of the *Klebsiella* genus normally express two different types of antigens. The first is a capsular polysaccharide, and the second is a lipopolysaccharide (O antigens) (K antigen). These two antigens each add to pathogenicity. *Klebsiella* spp. are the leading cause of morbidity and mortality. For *Klebsiella* to be virulent, capsules are necessary. (5)

K. pneumoniae has emerged as a frequent source of hospital-acquired infections, including urinary tract infections (UTIs) and bloodstream infections (BSIs), where antibiotic-resistant strains are becoming more challenging to treat and are linked to a higher death rate. (12,13)

Simply because of the increasing exposure to pathogens connected with healthcare with time, there does appear to be a positive association between the amount of time a patient must stay in the hospital and the probability of contacting *K. pneumoniae* infection. (14) One of the main causes of neonatal sepsis (NS) is *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. In developed countries, this microbe causes neonatal sepsis in 4-9% of cases, but it affects 16–28% of people in underdeveloped nations. (15,16)

These microorganisms can be found in wood pulps, sawdust, and waters that receive these industrial effluents. Numerous isolates of *K. pneumoniae* and *K. oxytoca* have been isolated from untreated water samples collected from dams, seawater, sediment and intestinal contents of shrimps and freshwater fishes. As a result of its capacity to form capsules and subsequent biofilm, the organism can survive in water distribution system despite chlorination. (18)

Extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL)-producing organism infections are an issue on a global scale. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, which produces ESBLs, are being linked to rising antibiotic resistance. (21) ESBLs are usually plasmid mediated. Since these plasmids are easily transmitted among different members of the Enterobacteriaceae, accumulation of resistance genes results in strains that contain multidrug resistant plasmids. For this reason, ESBL-producing isolates are resistant to a variety of classes of antibiotics.

Moreover, the emergence of these multiply resistant *Klebsiella* strains is unfortunately accompanied by a relatively high stability of the plasmids encoding ESBLs. Even years after the discontinuation of ceftazidime and other extended spectrum cephalosporins,

continued colonization of patients by ESBL-producing *Klebsiella* strains has been observed. Risk factors for acquisition of these strains seem to be the length of stay in hospital and the performance of invasive procedures. (22)

Antibiotic resistance in *K. pneumoniae* has grown against various antibiotic families. The majority of these antibiotic resistance mechanisms (AMR) were acquired through horizontal gene transfer (HGT), which confers high level resistance to β -lactam and quinolone antibiotics.

Penicillin binding proteins (PBPs), which are specialized targets of β -lactam antibiotics and enzymes that catalyze the formation of peptidoglycans, are one of the resistance strategies used by *K. pneumoniae*. PBPs' affinity for lactam antibiotics is reduced by structural changes, which leads to an increase in resistance to them. (23,24)

Additionally, alterations in outer membrane (OM) permeability play a crucial role in *K. pneumoniae* resistance (hydrophilic drugs). (25) Before it can bind to PBPs, OM is a barrier that must be overcome. Porins (OmpK35 and OmpK36), which the antibiotic molecules must employ, are either less in number or changed, reducing the membrane's permeability. (26,27) Quinolone resistance also results from altered permeability and the presence of efflux pumps. (28)

Previous studies have shown that *K. pneumoniae* strains that are resistant to a broad spectrum of antibiotics are rapidly expanding, especially when the bacteria are capable of forming biofilm. These bacteria can form a thick layer of extracellular biofilm which helps them attach to living and abiotic surfaces. Treatment of infections caused by biofilm-forming *K. pneumoniae* strains is more difficult than other strains. The antibiotic resistance and bacterial tendency to biofilm formation may play a key role in the emergence of MDR-*K. pneumoniae* strains.

Due to the antiphagocytic feature of biofilm, it is more challenging for the host immunity to eliminate this kind of bacterial pathogens. The use of antibiotics in patients with bacterial infections can lead to bacterial elimination and accelerate the treatment process. Consequently, the increasing incidence of drug resistance causes complications in patients and higher medical costs. (29)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of 143 samples were included which was calculated by the WHO sample size calculator. All these samples were taken from Microbiology laboratory of Tertiary Care Hospital, Rawalpindi. The ethical committee of university gave their approval to this study. Patient informed consent was obtained before any data was gathered.

The Cross-sectional descriptive study is performed on this sample population. The *Klebsiella* species isolated from all clinical samples were included and clinical samples taken from all age groups were included in this study. Microorganisms other than *Klebsiella* were excluded.

METHODOLOGY

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing performed after the isolation of *Klebsiella* species by Disk Diffusion method using Kirby-Bauer technique. The organism was inoculated on MH agar plates by sterile swabs and then discs were placed on media and pressed gently followed by overnight incubation at 37°C. The antibiotics included amoxicillin-clavulanic acid (30 µg), amikacin (30 µg), gentamycin (30 µg), ceftriaxone (30 µg), ceftazidime (30 µg), cefotaxime (30 µg), imipenem (10 µg), cefepime (30 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (cotrimoxazole) (25 µg), piperacillin-tazobactam (110 µg), cefoparazone-sulbactam (105 µg), tigecycline (TGC), colistin (10 µg), Fosfomycin, nitrofurantoin (300 µg). The zone of inhibitions of each antibiotic was recorded in millimeter (mm) and corresponds to CLSI standard value of respective antibiotic.

RESULTS

According to this research *K. pneumoniae* is prevalent in females that is 55%. According to antibiogram results of 143 isolates of *K. pneumoniae*, the highest antibiotic resistance was related to augmentin (amoxicillin/clavulanic acid) (98%) and 96.60% isolates were susceptible to colistin. All the data is tabulated and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 25). Frequency and percentage were calculated for categorical data.

Figure 1: This above figure shows the source of isolates included in this work. Out of 143 samples

K. pneumoniae clinical isolates, 8 (5.6%) were collected from throat culture, 63 (44.1%) from urine, 3 (2.1%) from blood culture, 26 (18.2%) from pus culture, 24 (16.8%) from wound, 16 (11.2%) from aspirates/ body fluids, 16 (11.2%) from tip (ETT, CVP, Folley's catheter) culture and 1 (0.7%) from bile sample.

Figure 2

Figure 2: shows prevalence of *K. pneumoniae* in male and female patients. About 64 (44.8%) *K. pneumoniae* strains were obtained from male and 79 (55.2%) from female patients. Among all the clinical isolates 54 (37.8%) were taken from outpatients and 89 (62.2%) from inpatients specimens

Table 1:

ANTIBIOTICS	SENSITIVE	RESISTANT
COLISTIN	96.60%	3.40%
TIGECYCLINE	75.50%	16.10%
AMIKACIN	78.10%	21.90%
GENTAMICIN	82%	18%
SULZONE	69.20%	30.8%
TAZOCIN	63.20%	36.80%
CEFTRIAZONE	12.51%	87.49%
CEFTAZIDIME	13.7%	86.30%
CEFEPIME	13.34%	86.66%
CEFOTAXIME	3%	97%
CEFEXIME	3.30%	96.70%
AUGMENTIN	2%	98%
CIPROFLOXACIN	21%	79%
IMIPENEM	56%	44%
COTRIMOXAZOLE	11%	89%

Table 1: The frequency of antimicrobial susceptibility of different antibiotics are shown in above table 1. According to antibiogram results of 143 isolates of *K. pneumoniae*, the highest antibiotic resistance was related to augmentin (amoxicillin/clavulanic acid) (98%) and 96.60% isolates were susceptible to colistin. After augmentin, the most resistance was to cefotaxime (97%) and cefexime (96.70%)

Figure 3

Figure 3: Antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The prevalence of antimicrobial susceptibility pattern to tigecycline, amikacin, gentamicin sulzone, tazocin, ceftriaxone, cefepime, ceftazidime, ciprofloxacin, imipenem and cotrimoxazole are shown in figure 3. Different antibiotic susceptibility pattern in various clinical specimens, for example out of 63 urine samples 73.2% were resistant to nitrofurantoin and 61.5% resistant to Fosfomycin, was observed. In addition to colistin, 82% isolates show susceptibility to gentamicin, 78.10% isolates to amikacin, 75.50% to tigecycline, sulzone (69.20%), tazocin (63.20%) and 56% to imipenem.

DISCUSSION

Klebsiella has emerged as a potential virulent pathogen over the years. Previously, a common cause of community acquired pneumonia, urinary tract infections, bacteremia and neonatal septicemia, hypervirulent forms with a potential for metastatic spread has occurred. These hypervirulent forms are primarily the cause of amoebic liver abscess, meningitis and metastatic endophthalmitis. An insight of different virulence factors and their mechanism of interference with the host immune mechanism responsible for disease causation would enable to curb their harmful effects. The *K. pneumoniae* isolates used in this study came from wide range of samples (figure1). The main sample sources were urine (44.1%), pus (18.2%), wound culture (16.8%), tips culture (11.2%), throat culture (5.6%), blood culture (2.1%), fluids/aspirates (1.45) and from bile (0.7%). In this study 96.60% isolates were susceptible to colistin and the highest antibiotic resistance was related to augmentin (98%), cefotaxime (97%), and cefexime (96.70%). The results of this study were consistent with that conducted at two major Hamadan hospitals, west of Iran from September 2018 to march 2019. A total of 83 *K. pneumoniae* isolates were collected from different clinical specimens. The highest antibiotic resistance was related to cefotaxime (92%) and all isolates were susceptible to colistin. This study also shows that clinical isolates obtained from inpatient department are more prevalent as compared to

that of outpatient department which is consistent with our present study. Another study was conducted at Bolan Medical Complex, Quetta, Balochistan. Clinical samples (n=107) of urine and sputum were collected and processed for *K. pneumoniae* isolation using selective culture media. All the isolates (100%) were resistant to amoxicillin, cefixime, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, cefotaxime, and ceftriaxone followed by ciprofloxacin (76.2%), sulphamethoxazole (66.7%), norfloxacin (42.9%).

A similar study was conducted at department of Microbiology, Dhaka Medical University, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Among 316 samples that yielded culture positivity, *K. pneumoniae* were identified as second most common organism. Most of the isolates were resistant to sulphamethoxazole-trimethoprim (90.67%) and ceftriaxone (90.67%) followed by cefotaxime (89.33%) and ceftazidime (89.33%). The most sensitive antibiotic for the isolates was tigecycline.

This study also highlights greater prevalence of *K. pneumoniae* in females (55.2%) than males (44.8%). A similar study conducted on 130 clinical isolates of *K. pneumoniae* obtained from various specimens in Duhok City, Iraq during January 2017-February 2019 which show that the isolates were more predominant in females (n=99) compared to males (n=31). The resistance rate of *K. pneumoniae* varied among different isolate clinical sample sources. Overall high resistance rates were reported for ampicillin (96.9%), ceftriaxone (65.8%) and cefepime (60.8%). However, imipenem showed highest susceptibility rate against the isolates. In June 2015, a carbapenem resistant *K. pneumoniae* was isolated from the tracheal secretion and an endotracheal tube of a 32-year-old female patient at the intensive care unit at the tertiary hospital, Pakistan Institute of Medical sciences, Islamabad. Isolates were found to be multi-drug resistant and sensitive only to Tigecycline and Colistin.

A retrospective study focused on drug susceptibility of *K. pneumoniae* isolated from intensive care unit (ICU) patients with bloodstream infection in Shanghai, China showed that out of 78 *K. pneumoniae* isolates, the highest resistance is related to amoxicillin-clavulanate (93.5%), aztreonam (93.5%) and ciprofloxacin (92.3%). In contrast, relatively low resistance to colistin (11.5%) and tigecycline (23%).

CONCLUSION

The results of this study show that most isolated species of *Klebsiella* is *Klebsiella pneumoniae* among isolates obtained from various clinical specimens at tertiary care hospital, Rawalpindi. *K. pneumoniae*, the cause of urinary tract infection and pneumonia, is becoming resistant to various antibiotics with most resistance to amoxicillin-clavulanate, cefotaxime and cefixime due to β lactamase production. Colistin is the most effective drug against *Klebsiella* according to our study with some susceptibility to amikacin, gentamicin, imipenem, sulzone and tazocin. The prevalence of *K. pneumoniae* among females is greater as compared to males and most prevalent in admitted patients than outpatient's specimens.

Our results suggested that there is high antibiotics resistance among *K. pneumoniae* isolates towards commonly prescribed antibiotics, which is an alarming situation for developing countries like Pakistan. Continuous monitoring and strict antimicrobial policy will have a great impact on reducing antimicrobial resistance towards antibiotics and development of proper treatment options against *K. pneumoniae* infections.

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